

Regional inequality of the European ETS-2

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The regressive nature of ETS-2 disproportionately affects lower-income households.
- Regions with fossil fuel reliance and limited low-carbon infrastructure face high burdens.
- Regions from Bulgaria, Hungary, and Poland are among the most exposed regions.
- Vulnerable regions require direct subsidies and renewable energy incentives.
- Long-term solutions include energy-efficient housing and better public transport.

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the distributional impacts of the EU's second Emissions Trading System (ETS-2) on households across 1160 European regions, with a focus on the interaction between climate policy and social equity. Using household survey data, economic modeling, and spatial mapping, it evaluates the effects of a projected € 100 per ton CO₂ price by 2030 on heating and transportation expenditures. Results indicate that low-income, rural households and larger families are disproportionately affected, with the strongest impacts observed in lower-GDP regions of Central and Eastern Europe. These findings confirm the regressive potential of carbon pricing and underscore the need for regionally tailored compensation measures. The Social Climate Fund (SCF), already established to mitigate such impacts, could benefit from these insights to guide the design and allocation of its resources, supporting an ETS-2 implementation that advances a climate transition which is both environmentally effective and socially equitable.

1. Introduction

The European Union Emissions Trading System-2 (EU ETS-2) is a new carbon pricing mechanism designed to cover emissions from buildings and road transport sectors, complementing the existing EU ETS (European Commission, 2021c). Set to become fully operational in 2027, the EU ETS-2 will operate on a 'cap-and-trade' principle, targeting upstream emissions. It aims to reduce emissions in these sectors by 42 % by 2030 compared to 2005 levels, through full auction of allowances. To ensure price stability, a mechanism has been incorporated to release additional allowances if prices exceed € 45 per ton of CO₂ during the first three years of operation (Edenhofer et al., 2021; Eden et al., 2023).

The implementation of EU ETS-2, however, has raised significant concerns about its potential to exacerbate economic inequality. Critics argue that the system could disproportionately burden low-income

households, which may rather spend a higher share of their income on fossil fuels for heating and transport (van den Bergh et al., 2024). These concerns lie in a fundamental consideration in climate policies due to their multifaceted relationship with climate change (Feindt et al., 2021), following a broad consensus that energy policies impact sectors, household groups, and geographical regions differently. A poorly designed climate policy can exacerbate existing inequalities, while a well-designed one that addresses both climate change and inequality can foster more equitable societies and increase public support for climate action.

Add to this, the energy transition has the potential to exacerbate regional inequalities (Keuchel and Lohrmann, 2024) and intensify resistance to European policies and infrastructure development (Rodríguez-Pose and Bartalucci, 2024). With the introduction of a new carbon

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price under the EU ETS-2, which will apply to household heating and transportation expenditures, there is a heightened risk of disproportionately impacting lower-income households and economically disadvantaged regions (Antosiewicz et al., 2022). Understanding the distributional effects of ETS-2 is therefore crucial to ensuring that the policy achieves its climate objectives while mitigating social and regional disparities. A comprehensive analysis of these effects is essential for inclusive planning processes (Hanna Lempinen and Korpikoski, 2025) including the design of compensatory mechanisms to enhance public acceptance of this critical transition toward a low-carbon economy (Muth et al., 2024). In this context, the implementation of the EU ETS-2 requires a rigorous assessment of its implications for inequality.

This paper examines the impact of the new ETS-2 price on household expenditures through a detailed distributional analysis, mapping 1160 regions across Europe. This approach addresses a significant gap in existing research, which predominantly focuses on inequalities between countries or among different household types (e.g., Emmerling et al. (2024)), without accounting for regional disparities. The objective is to provide a comprehensive understanding of how household size, composition, and regional characteristics shape the overall effects of ETS-2 on energy consumption and related costs. Specifically, the analysis examines the impact of the ETS-2 price on household spending for heating and transportation, incorporating both household-level and regional heterogeneity. By complementing recent studies that assess the distributional effects of ETS-2 based on income deciles or quintiles at the Member State level (e.g., Görlach et al. (2022); Held et al. (2022)), this study scrutinizes the regions most affected due to regional inequalities. In this context, we also reflect on the current design of the Social Climate Fund (SCF) and tentatively suggest that its effectiveness could be enhanced by more explicitly considering regional inequalities. While the SCF may offer a channel to address some of these disparities, its actual impact will likely depend on how allocation criteria are interpreted and implemented.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the current EU ETS-2 proposal and reviews existing studies on its impacts, highlighting research gaps that inform the analytical scope and research question. Section 3 describes the methodology employed, followed by Section 4, which presents the analysis and results. Finally, Section 5 offers the conclusions of the study.

2. New architecture of EU ETS-2 and current impact analysis

2.1. From concept to action: the role of ETS-2 in achieving 2030 goals

As part of the Fit for 55 package (European Commission, 2021b), the EU introduced a new ETS for buildings and road transport (ETS-2), aimed at reducing emissions in these sectors starting in 2027. This initiative complements existing measures within the Fit for 55 framework, which seeks to cut EU greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55 % by 2030 compared to 1990 levels (Agora Energiewende and Ecologic Institute, 2021). Other key elements include strengthening the existing ETS, raising renewable energy targets to 40 %, ¹ enhancing energy efficiency, introducing a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), banning new internal combustion engine cars by 2035, and establishing SCF to mitigate the social impacts of ETS-2.

As it is designed to complement the existing ETS by covering CO₂ emissions that are not included in the existing ETS (Leenders et al., 2024), the CO₂ emissions that are included in ETS-2 come from buildings (primarily heating), road transport, and some additional sectors that include mainly include small industries. The ETS-2 will cover emissions upstream (Braungardt et al., 2024), meaning that the obligation to surrender allowances will fall on the fuel suppliers rather than

end-consumers. Allowances will initially be primarily freely allocated, but will transition to full auction.²

To mitigate excessive price increases, additional allowances may be released from the market stability reserve if prices exceed € 45 during this period. The ETS-2 cap targets a 42 % emissions reduction by 2030 compared to 2005 levels. To address the social impacts associated with this policy, the SCF has been established, financed through ETS-2 revenues. Member States can utilize this fund to support energy efficiency improvements, building renovations, the adoption of clean heating systems, the integration of renewable energy, and the promotion of zero-emission mobility. Additionally, the fund may provide direct income support to vulnerable groups, if necessary.

2.2. The ETS-2: current analysis

Initial works analysing ETS-2 have focused on the broader Fit for 55 package, emphasizing the costs associated with increasing abatement efforts (Boitier et al., 2023), rather than explicitly assessing the specific impacts of the EU ETS-2. A notable recent study by Chateau et al. (2023) provided a comprehensive analysis using the OECD's ENV-Linkages model as part of the Fit for 55 framework, yet it only offers a general overview of the EU's climate targets and does not delve into the detailed impacts of EU ETS-2. Crucially, there is no estimation of the EU ETS-2 price and, therefore, the study omits an analysis of its economic implications. The study merely reports that 5 % of the abatement target under EU ETS-2 could be achieved, estimating that a carbon price should be lower than the current EU ETS market price (projected at € 178 in 2030).

Other initial studies, however, offer valuable insights relevant to the broader scope of EU climate policy, including the planned expansion to the ETS-2. The EU's introduction of the ETS-2 aims to address the challenge of reducing carbon emissions in the buildings and transport by imposing a carbon price on these sectors. The impact of carbon pricing will primarily fall on consumers (Funke et al., 2024), and it could disproportionately affect vulnerable households, particularly those with lower incomes (Ohlendorf et al., 2020) or higher energy dependencies (Semet, 2024).

Likewise, Temursho et al. (2020) provides a comprehensive assessment of the distributional effects of ambitious EU-wide climate targets, using integrated macro-micro modeling with household budget survey data. The study evaluates welfare impacts across income and expenditure deciles, highlighting both vertical and horizontal equity concerns, particularly in relation to residential energy and transport fuel expenditures. Although the analysis does not explicitly focus on ETS-2, it closely mirrors the type of distributional dynamics that the mechanism now brings to the fore.

The European Commission's formal impact assessment (European Commission, 2021a) offers a comprehensive analysis of heating and transport energy trends, policy impacts, and related emissions, forming a key reference for EU climate and energy planning. It includes detailed projections of household energy expenditures, covering fuel and vehicle costs as well as investments in energy efficiency. While not limited to ETS-2, the report highlights the distinct impacts of heating and transport prices—particularly noting that low-income households often do not incur transport fuel expenditures.

Meanwhile, the EU ETS-2 price mechanism will function similarly to a fuel tax due to its upstream implementation on fuel suppliers, who are expected to pass the costs to consumers through higher fuel prices (Abrell et al., 2024). This system will apply uniformly across the EU, increasing prices for various fuels used in buildings and transport. Like a fuel tax, it will create a financial incentive for consumers to reduce

¹ The final legislation in place now contains a 42.5 % target (<https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy>).

² ETS-2 will not include free allowances; all permits will be auctioned. Part of the revenues will finance the Social Climate Fund, which allocates more support to poorer Member States. Up to 37.5 % of national plans may be used for temporary direct income support to vulnerable groups.

fuel consumption or switch to cleaner alternatives, while also generating revenue for climate action and social measures. The key difference is that ETS-2 specifically targets CO₂ emissions, but its effect on consumers and the market will closely resemble that of a traditional fuel tax.

A key consideration is the regressive nature of these fuel taxes (Fratesi, 2025) and their uneven impact across income groups (Andrés Rodríguez-Pose and Poelman, 2024). Jacobs et al. (2022) highlights that the current fuel tax regime disproportionately affects low-income households, particularly through petrol taxes, whereas diesel taxes exhibit a progressive effect. Using Germany as a case study, the research demonstrates that fuel taxes represent a larger proportion of disposable income for low-income households compared to wealthier ones. Weitzel et al. (2023) also finds that extending carbon pricing to fuels used in buildings and transport leads to higher prices for fuels, electricity, and transport services. These price increases tend to have regressive effects, as lower-income households allocate a larger share of their expenditure to these energy-related goods. Similarly, Sterner (2012) and Linden et al. (2024) confirm that fuel taxes are generally regressive in high-income countries, though their effects vary significantly across socio-economic groups. These findings emphasize the need to understand such impacts to develop measures that mitigate adverse effects on vulnerable households.

Addressing the distributional effects of carbon taxes is essential, as implementing such measures without addressing their regressive nature risks exacerbating social and economic inequalities (Wallenko and Bachner, 2025). Vona (2023) emphasizes the complexity of distributional impacts in climate policies, underscoring the importance of approaches that account for household characteristics and consumption patterns. Similarly, Amores et al. (2023) highlight that the redistributive effects of energy taxation are closely tied to household expenditure allocation, particularly for energy-related expenses. The challenge lies in designing socially equitable carbon pricing mechanisms (Baranzini et al., 2017), as poorly implemented policies could exacerbate energy and transport poverty if not accompanied by robust compensatory measures (Feindt et al., 2021).

The ETS-2 introduces a carbon price on emissions from direct fuel combustion, including fossil fuel heating in buildings, aiming to incentivize the transition to cleaner heating systems. However, carbon pricing could lead to substantial increases in energy bills, potentially exceeding the levels seen during the 2022 energy crisis if decarbonization efforts fall short and prices escalate (Keliauskaitė et al., 2025).

2.3. Advancing beyond existing assessment: identifying research gap

Several assessment reports have analyzed the distributional effects of ETS-2, consistently highlighting its regressive nature in the context of carbon pricing. A recent report by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (Eden et al., 2023) estimates the distributional impacts of ETS-2, emphasizing its disproportionate effect on low-income households due to rising energy costs. The report advocates for targeted support through the SCF and increased stakeholder engagement to address energy and transport poverty. Similarly, an assessment by the German Government Council (Held et al., 2022) identifies criteria for equitable carbon pricing, emphasizing the need for a holistic policy mix, fair cost distribution among EU member states, and further refinement of the SCF to mitigate regressive impacts on vulnerable groups.

Recent study by Rüb (2024) provides a comparative analysis of a carbon tax on transport and heating fuels across seven EU countries (Germany, France, Spain, Poland, Finland, Hungary, and Ireland), using Eurostat's Household Budget Survey (HBS) data and advanced inequality measures. The study finds that implementing a carbon tax without revenue recycling consistently exacerbates inequality, though the extent varies across countries. These findings align with reports from the Institute for European Environmental Policy (Gore et al., 2022) and the Institute for Sustainable Development and International

Relations (Berghmans, 2022), which explore the interaction between ETS-2 and Energy Taxation Directive (ETD) reforms. Their analyses suggest that while reducing electricity taxes may benefit low-income households, increased fossil fuel taxes could disproportionately burden rural and middle-income households, highlighting the necessity of robust redistribution measures.

Further supporting this perspective, Stenning et al. (2021) from Cambridge University demonstrates that revenue recycling—through tax reductions, lump-sum transfers, or investments in low-carbon technologies—can mitigate adverse effects on GDP and employment while facilitating a just transition for households and industries. Similarly, Frondel and Schubert (2021) and Vandyck et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of compensatory measures in alleviating the regressive impacts of carbon pricing and balancing economic efficiency with social equity. Together, these studies underscore the critical role of redistribution mechanisms in ensuring that carbon pricing policies under ETS-2 are both economically viable and socially equitable.

Despite the valuable insights provided by these studies, significant research gaps remain. Key among these are a specific focus on the ETS-2, impacts on sectoral and geographic variations, as well as the effects on diverse household compositions, particularly in energy-poor regions. Previous studies by Temursho et al. (2020) and Weitzel et al. (2023) examine broader climate policy packages of regulatory, carbon pricing, and mixed approaches, and their aggregate socio-economic impacts on GDP, employment, and income distribution. However, they do not isolate the specific effects of ETS-2 or provide a focused analysis of heating and transport fuel price shocks at the household level. While regional disaggregation is included, it remains part of a wider assessment without a sector-specific focus.

In terms of geographic variation perspective, regional analysis is essential for identifying areas that are structurally disadvantaged in accessing affordable, efficient, or modern energy services. It is often referred to as energy peripheries (Bouzarovski and Tirado Herrero, 2017), in which policies like carbon pricing or emissions trading schemes such as ETS-2 can produce uneven spatial impacts, placing a disproportionate burden on these already vulnerable regions. The analysis of Rüb (2024) highlights that the distributional effects of a carbon tax vary across countries due to differences in energy consumption patterns and economic conditions, but it is limited to a select group of countries rather than offering a broader regional assessment of ETS-2's impact on household expenditures across Europe. LaBelle et al. (2022), by contrast, provides a broader regional assessment that highlights the vulnerability of post-communist member states to rising energy costs and associated inequalities, yet it does not specifically examine the ETS-2 mechanism.

Moreover, it is crucial to examine the differentiated effects of ETS-2 on household expenditures related to heating and transport across EU regions. While the German assessment report (Eden et al., 2023) briefly touches on this issue, it lacks the depth needed for a comprehensive, EU-wide understanding. Expanding regional analysis is particularly important given that transport poverty (Primc et al., 2025; Vandyck et al., 2023) or car dependency (Mattioli et al., 2020) are closely tied to spatial inequalities, especially in rural or poorly connected areas with limited public transport options. As the costs of ETS-2 will ultimately fall on households, analyses must move beyond broad income categories to consider diverse household compositions (e.g., single-parent families). Although energy poverty is recognized in the literature, further research is needed to assess how ETS-2 impacts energy-poor households across different regional contexts.

Our analysis addresses these gaps by providing a detailed, spatially disaggregated, and sector-specific assessment of the EU's ETS-2 and its impacts, accompanied by tailored policy recommendations to deal with regional inequalities. In contrast to previous studies, we offer a high-resolution regional analysis at the NUTS-3 level, covering 1160 European regions and capturing both rural and urban contexts. The analysis focuses specifically on emissions from buildings (primarily heating) and road transport, while accounting for diverse household

compositions. Integrating income levels, regional disparities, and household structures is essential for designing effective policies to enhance energy efficiency in both the building and transport sectors (Rosenow et al., 2017; Günther et al., 2025). The analysis examines the socio-economic and spatial distributional effects of the more targeted carbon pricing mechanism under ETS-2, with a micro-level focus on household expenditures and regional disparities. It aims to complement existing literature by highlighting equity and social justice concerns, which have been less emphasized in previous studies focused on broader, EU-wide policy frameworks.

3. Data and methodology

To provide a deeper understanding of how household size, composition, and regional characteristics influence the overall impact of ETS-2 on energy consumption and related costs, this paper employs a comprehensive methodology integrating household survey data, econometric estimates, and geographic information systems (GIS).

First, based on a review of existing literature, including Günther et al. (2025) and Rüb (2024), the analysis assumes an ETS-2 carbon price of € 100 per ton of CO₂ by 2030. This value represents the average within a projected range of € 71 to € 261 per ton, depending on the stringency of complementary energy efficiency policies, often used as a reference point to evaluate the economic implications of carbon pricing and its effectiveness in achieving emission reduction targets while considering social equity. Strong policies are expected to lower the carbon price, while less stringency could result in significantly higher costs.

Second, data from the International Energy Agency (IEA)³ on household energy prices are utilized to estimate the expected price increases for heating and transport fuels across the 27 EU Member States. These price estimates are integrated into the WILLIAM European Household Database (Tomás et al., 2021) which segments households into 60 categories based on three dimensions: income quintiles, urban versus rural locations, and family composition.

The survey categorizes households' database into five income groups and defines urban areas as those with a population density of at least 500 inhabitants per square kilometer. Additionally, it classifies households into six types based on family composition. For each of these 60 household types, the anticipated increases in heating and transport costs due to the ETS-2 carbon price are calculated. These expenditure increases are then analyzed through econometric estimations to examine how various household characteristics shape the distributional impacts, offering a detailed assessment of the financial burden imposed by ETS-2 across different household types in Europe.

To further enhance the analysis, the results of econometric modeling are combined with a GIS-based spatial analysis at the NUTS-3 level, using data from the Eurostat database. This integration allows for the mapping of ETS-2 impacts across 1160 European regions, identifying areas most affected by increased heating and transport costs. The analysis incorporates several indicators, including the percentage increase in household expenditures and an exposure index that highlights regions most vulnerable to these impacts. This methodology, which integrates household survey data, econometric estimates, and GIS to assess the regional impacts of ETS-2 on household expenditures, provides a valuable approach for identifying spatial disparities. By incorporating these analytical tools, it addresses the need for a more comprehensive assessment of climate policies within a broader socioeconomic context, as highlighted in Mikropoulos et al. (2025).

Fig. 1 provides an overview of this methodological framework, illustrating the step-by-step process used to evaluate the distributional effects of ETS-2. This approach ensures a nuanced understanding of the economic implications, accounting for disparities in income, location, and family structure across Europe.

Fig. 1. Methodological overview.

4. Results and analysis

4.1. Impact of an ETS-2 price on households energy prices

Using data from the IEA and Eurostat databases, consumer prices for automobile diesel, motor gasoline, natural gas, heating oil, and coal were computed for the year 2023 for each European country. With an ETS-2 carbon price of € 100 per ton of CO₂ and factoring in the CO₂ content of each fossil fuel, the resulting price increases for heating and transport fuels were calculated. The analysis accounts for the level of dieselization in each country (i.e., the share of diesel cars in the total passenger car fleet). It does not incorporate the share of biofuels in diesel and petrol, which varies across Member States and remains limited (Lundberg et al., 2023), but the proportion of coal in solid fuel consumption, which also includes wood, is taken into account. The “opt-out” provision of ETS-2 legislation is not considered. This provision allows a Member State that already applies a CO₂ tax to forgo the ETS-2 price if its domestic CO₂ tax exceeds the ETS-2 price (Nysten, 2024). To date, only Ireland has requested such a derogation from ETS-2.

Table 1 presents these price increases. For petroleum fuels, the increases are relatively comparable, ranging from 12.3 % to 19.1 % for transport fuels and 13.5 % to 29.3 % for heating oil. However, the projected increases in natural gas prices show significant variation, reflecting differences in countries' access to gas supplies and their tax structures. For instance, gas prices are projected to rise by 60.5 % in Hungary and 44.9 % in Croatia, while the increases in Sweden and Finland are much lower, at 9.5 %.

Coal used for heating is (Heating Solid) limited in most European countries, accounting for an average of just 2.5 % of household energy consumption in the EU (Gajdzik et al., 2023). However, its share is considerably higher in certain countries, such as Poland (24.6 %), Ireland (11.6 %), the Czech Republic (8.9 %), and Bulgaria (4.2 %), resulting in correspondingly higher increases in solid fuel prices in these regions.

These calculated price increases were integrated into a household budget survey, enabling the estimation of the additional spending on heating and transport for households across different countries. This approach provides a detailed assessment of the financial burden that ETS-2 could impose on household energy expenditures.

4.2. Impact on households expenditures

Next step is integrating the change in energy price into the WILLIAM European Household Database (Tomás et al., 2021). This database was developed within the Horizon 2020 European project LOCOMOTION⁴

³ <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/data-product/energy-prices>.

⁴ see: <https://www.locomotion-h2020.eu/>.

Table 1
Fossil fuel price increase for households with an ETS-2 price equal to 100 €.

	Heating solid	Heating gas	Heating oil	Transport fuel
Austria (AUT)	0.2 %	12.3 %	20.6 %	15.3 %
Belgium (BEL)	1.7 %	18.8 %	26.4 %	14.3 %
Bulgaria (BGR)	3.0 %	25.5 %	23.9 %	18.2 %
Croatia (HRV)	0.1 %	44.9 %	29.3 %	16.3 %
Cyprus (CYP)	0.0 %	18.6 %	23.3 %	16.2 %
Czech Republic (CZE)	21.3 %	15.5 %	24.1 %	15.8 %
Denmark (DNK)	0.0 %	14.1 %	13.5 %	12.2 %
Estonia (EST)	0.1 %	21.5 %	21.9 %	14.6 %
Finland (FIN)	0.1 %	9.5 %	17.4 %	12.3 %
France (FRA)	0.1 %	17.4 %	19.7 %	13.8 %
Germany (DEU)	1.4 %	15.1 %	24.1 %	13.4 %
Greece (GRC)	0.1 %	18.6 %	19.6 %	12.6 %
Hungary (HUN)	4.9 %	60.5 %	15.4 %	15.2 %
Ireland (IRL)	27.1 %	13.5 %	24.4 %	14.8 %
Italy (ITA)	0.0 %	16.2 %	16.1 %	13.4 %
Latvia (LVA)	0.1 %	17.0 %	21.9 %	15.4 %
Lithuania (LTU)	2.0 %	11.7 %	26.0 %	16.6 %
Luxembourg (LUX)	0.5 %	13.9 %	26.6 %	16.1 %
Malta (MLT)	0.0 %	18.6 %	25.7 %	19.1 %
Netherlands (NLD)	0.0 %	11.5 %	26.4 %	12.7 %
Poland (POL)	31.4 %	27.8 %	20.4 %	16.9 %
Portugal (PRT)	0.0 %	14.5 %	15.7 %	15.1 %
Romania (ROU)	0.4 %	36.5 %	18.5 %	17.4 %
Slovak Republic (SVK)	8.1 %	16.4 %	24.1 %	14.9 %
Slovenia (SVN)	0.0 %	19.9 %	22.6 %	15.1 %
Spain (ESP)	0.7 %	18.6 %	23.7 %	15.6 %
Sweden (SWE)	0.0 %	9.5 %	22.2 %	13.3 %

that enables the classification of 60 distinct household types across each European Member State from the EU Household Budget Survey (HBS) by integrating three key dimensions. First, it categorizes households into five income groups: the first quintile (Q1), second quintile (Q2), third quintile (Q3), fourth quintile (Q4), and fifth quintile (Q5). Second, the database differentiates between urban and rural households, with urban areas defined as those having at least 500 inhabitants per square kilometer. Lastly, it distinguishes between six household types: single adults without children (S1), single adults with children (S2), couples without children (C1), couples with children (C2), other types of households without children (O1), and other types of households with children (O2).

The database does not include data for six European countries: Austria and the Netherlands are missing due to a lack of data, while Italy, Romania, Slovenia, and Malta are incomplete. The data, which is from the year 2015, is expressed in US\$₂₀₁₅ and includes final consumption expenditure by households, categorized by consumption purpose according to the Classification of Individual Consumption According to Purpose (COICOP). Additionally, it provides information on household size, income receipts, and savings, with a detailed list of variables available in [Appendix A](#).

From this database, expenditures on heating fuels (solid fuels, gas, liquid fuels) and transport fuels are extracted for the 60 household types. Disposable income data is also incorporated. [Figs. 2 and 3](#) illustrate the percentage increase in expenditure relative to disposable income across income quintiles. The impacts vary significantly across Member States. In particular, the carbon price on heating is highly regressive, though there are notable exceptions in countries like Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Slovakia, and Sweden. Similarly, the impact on transport expenditure is also regressive, with exceptions in Bulgaria, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Poland, and Slovakia. The orders of magnitude observed are comparable to those cited in the WWF impact studies ([WWF, 2022](#)), although variations in country hierarchies may arise due to differences in assumptions and data sources, making direct comparisons inconclusive. Additional figures scrutinizing other dimensions (location, family composition) are provided in [Appendix B](#).

Table 2
Data used in the regressions.

Variable	Description	Source	Unit
E_H	Heating fuel expenditure increase	WILIAM database	US \$ converted in € 2015
E_T	Transport fuel expenditure increase	WILIAM database	US \$ converted in € 2015
I	Disposable income	WILIAM database	US \$ converted in € 2015
U_r	Type of area	WILIAM database	Urban = 1, Rural = 0
F	Family composition	WILIAM database	†
HDD	Heating degree days (year 2015)	Eurostat	degree
F_j	Country specific effects		1 if the household lives in this country

†: Single = 1; Single with children = 1.5; Couple = 2; Couple with children = 2.5; Other = 3; Other with children = 3.5.

4.3. Regression analysis of expenditure increases

A regression analysis is conducted to provide a comprehensive understanding of how household size, composition, and regional characteristics influence the overall effects of ETS-2 on energy consumption and related expenditures, specifically for heating and transport. The analysis utilizes a dataset comprising 1260 distinct household types, representing 60 household categories across 21 countries. Key explanatory variables include family composition (e.g., single, single with children, couple), urban or rural location, disposable income, heating degree days (applicable only for heating), and country-specific intercepts ([Table 2](#)). These variables enable a detailed evaluation of the variation in energy expenditure increases across different households and regions, shedding light on the distributional impacts of the ETS-2.

To address the heteroscedasticity identified in the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, the analysis applies a Weighted Least Squares (WLS) approach. This method assigns greater influence to observations with lower variance, thereby improving the efficiency and reliability of coefficient estimates. The general formula is as follows:

$$\hat{\beta}_{WLS} = (X^T W X)^{-1} X^T W y$$

where:

X : matrix of explanatory variables

y : vector of the dependent variable

W : diagonal matrix of weights w_i , typically defined as $w_i = \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}$

The weights are constructed using a simple inverse-variance formula, where each observation is weighted by the inverse of its estimated error variance.

4.3.1. Regression results: transport expenditure

[Table 3](#) presents the regression results for the relationship between household composition and regional characteristics and their impact on transport expenditures. The analysis reveals that larger households experience a greater increase in transport costs, while households in rural areas bear higher transportation costs compared to their urban counterparts. These findings align with previous studies, such as [Wadud et al. \(2009\)](#), which reported higher fuel consumption among rural households in the United States, and [Berry \(2019\)](#), which observed similar patterns in France. The econometric estimation demonstrates strong validity, with an R^2 value of 0.99, and all coefficients are statistically significant with expected signs, reinforcing the robustness of the results. A more recent study by [Keuchel and Lohrmann \(2024\)](#) also highlights these regional disparities, noting that households in rural areas are more affected by rising fuel prices compared to those in urban centers.

The inclusion of country fixed effects significantly enhances the model's explanatory power by accounting for unobserved, time-invariant country-specific factors. This approach minimizes the bias of

Fig. 2. Increase of heating expenditure in % of disposable income per quintile and country.

Fig. 3. Increase of transport expenditure in % of disposable income per quintile and country.

the omitted variables by controlling for characteristics unique to each country, thus isolating the variation within the country of the variables under analysis. The estimated coefficients reflect the average effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable within countries, rather than across countries. By capturing the distinct economic, social, and environmental contexts of each country, the fixed effects framework enables a more precise assessment of how household composition and regional characteristics shape energy expenditures.⁵

The high coefficient value for fixed effects in explaining transport costs suggests a greater unobserved, time-invariant heterogeneity across countries in transport-related expenditures. This indicates that country-specific factors, such as geography, infrastructure, or long-standing policies, exert a stronger influence on transport costs. Additionally,

⁵ Sweden is omitted from the regression to avoid perfect multicollinearity (the “dummy variable trap”). Coefficients on the remaining country dummies should therefore be interpreted relative to Sweden, which serves as the reference category. For example, the coefficient for Spain ($ESP = 192.14$) indicates that, after controlling for income, urbanization, and family size, Spanish households spend on average about 192 € more on transport than comparable Swedish households.

the variation in transport costs between countries, not captured by the observed variables, is more pronounced.

A similar regression analysis is then conducted on the increase in transport energy expenditure resulting from a 1 % rise in oil prices (denoted as $\overline{E_T}$), excluding country-specific effects among the explanatory variables. This estimation is designed to address gaps in the household budget survey for countries such as Austria, the Netherlands, Italy, Romania, Slovenia, and Malta. The results, shown in Table 4, still demonstrate adequate coefficient determination, with an R^2 value of 0.99, so it remains sufficiently robust for analytical purposes.⁶ Additionally, the coefficients maintain their expected signs, underscoring the reliability of the model for application to the excluded countries.

⁶ The higher R-squared values reported for the WLS estimations do not stem from a change in the set of explanatory variables, which are identical to those in the OLS specification. Rather, they reflect the weighting scheme. WLS minimizes a weighted sum of squared residuals and computes goodness-of-fit measures using weighted sums of squares. By assigning greater importance to observations with lower error variance, WLS yields a tighter fit relative to the weighted distribution of the dependent variable, which is reflected in higher R-squared values.

Table 3
Regression on transport expenditure E_T with country-specific effects.

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic
I	0.0077	231.6***
I^2	-3.4925 E-08	-89.7***
U_r	-31.0284	-153.1***
F	16.5134	68.9***
ESP	192.1380	115.2***
SVK	129.2740	229.0***
PRT	150.4420	223.3***
POL	169.2810	329.3***
LUX	351.6110	73.8***
LTU	189.0510	168.7***
LVA	147.6570	222.3***
IRL	52.7071	59.0***
HUN	197.6210	232.0***
GRC	163.1010	287.5***
DEU	184.006	402.7***
FRA	126.554	112.4***
FIN	108.177	191.0***
EST	188.6410	407.2***
DNK	25.40825	43.4***
CZE	139.223	203.5***
CYP	96.3287	215.9***
HRV	136.8880	201.6***
BGR	242.3400	163.9***
BEL	207.2040	77.0***
$Const$	-218.7470	331.8***
R-squared	0.99	
F-Statistic	255,300	
Degrees of freedom	1236	

Significantly different from 0 at *** 0.1 %, ** 1 %, * 5 %.

Table 4
Regression on transport expenditure $\overline{E_T}$ without country-specific effects for one percent price increase.

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic
I	3.6616 E-04	184.5***
I^2	-8.4736 E-10	-23.5***
U_r	-2.1095	-186.8***
F	1.5058	232.9***
$Const$	-2.4271	-94***
R-squared	0.99	
F-Statistic	216,028	
Degrees of freedom	1255	

Significantly different from 0 at *** 0.1 %, ** 1 %, * 5 %.

4.3.2. Regression results: heating expenditure

A distinct regression analysis is conducted for heating expenditures by normalizing energy expenditure based on heating degree days (HDD) and subsequently applying a logarithmic transformation to this variable. The explanatory variables also include the logarithm of disposable income to account for its influence on heating costs. The HDD variable captures different weather conditions within large countries (such as France or Italy) that cannot be represented by a country fixed effects. The use of the logarithmic relationship for heating expenditure is justified by a better econometric estimate than the absolute expenditure relationship used in the case of transport expenditure.

The results, presented in Table 5, reveal an R^2 value of 0.99, indicating a strong explanatory power for the model. All variables included in the estimation are statistically significant and exhibit the expected signs, effectively explaining variations in heating costs across household types and regions.

The analysis reveals a positive and statistically significant relationship between disposable income and heating expenditures, indicating that higher-income households tend to incur greater energy costs, consistent with increased energy consumption among wealthier households. The negative coefficient for urban residence highlights that urban households generally face lower heating costs compared to their rural

Table 5
Regression on heating expenditure ($\ln(E_H/HDD)$) with country-specific effects.

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic
$\ln(I)$	0.9266	190.0***
U_r	-0.3107	-116.1***
F	0.1117	49.8***
ESP	3.0344	427.4***
SVK	2.5969	347.6***
PRT	2.5371	163.8***
POL	3.4710	375.0***
LUX	2.2941	162.1***
LTU	1.6179	125.8***
LVA	1.7542	207.0***
IRL	1.8930	252.2***
HUN	3.5585	314.9***
GRC	2.5710	279.1***
DEU	2.6985	337.0***
FRA	2.6283	152.5***
FIN	0.3712	45.5***
EST	1.5588	191.6***
DNK	2.3034	282.4***
CZE	2.8996	374.4***
CYP	2.2343	149.5***
HRV	2.8926	324.3***
BGR	2.1920	169.3***
BEL	2.6012	415.5***
$Const$	-15.4971	-321.4***
R-squared	0.99	
F-Statistic	92,420	
Degrees of freedom	1236	

Significantly different from 0 at *** 0.1 %, ** 1 %, * 5 %.

Table 6
Regression on solid heating expenditure ($\ln(\overline{E_H}/HDD)$) without country-specific effects for one percent price increase.

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic
$\ln(I)$	0.3088	253.6***
U_r	-0.9465	-970.3***
F	0.1806	399.9***
$Const$	-11.2149	-943.3***
R-squared	0.99	
F-Statistic	2,731,000	
Degrees of freedom	1256	

Significantly different from 0 at *** 0.1 %, ** 1 %, * 5 %.

counterparts, likely due to differences in housing characteristics and heating system efficiencies. This finding aligns with Mata et al. (2021), who observed lower heating demands among urban households.

Furthermore, the positive and significant association between family composition and heating expenditures underscores the influence of household size on energy demand, as larger households require more energy resources. This aligns with findings by Mata et al. (2021) and Trotta et al. (2022), who demonstrated that variables reflecting dwelling size, such as floor area, number of bedrooms, or lot size, are positively correlated with energy demand, thereby explaining the impact of family size on heating costs in the estimation.

For countries excluded from the sample, the increase in energy expenditure resulting from a 1 % rise in energy prices is estimated separately for each fossil fuel type, including solid fuels, natural gas, and heating oil. The corresponding estimates are presented in Tables 6–8. While these estimates provide a basis for understanding expenditure changes, the quality of the model adjustments is also quite robust.

4.4. Impact at regional level: spatial disaggregation and mapping

The regional impact of an ETS-2 price on heating and transport energy expenditures is analyzed and mapped to provide a comprehensive understanding of its spatial distribution. This analysis integrates

Table 7
Regression on gas heating expenditure ($\ln(\overline{E_H}/HDD)$) without country-specific effects for one percent price increase.

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic
$\ln(I)$	0.1992	52.1***
U_r	-0.0161	-3.2**
F	1.2688	313.1***
$Const$	-12.4098	-369.0***
R-squared	0.99	
F-Statistic	53,100	
Degrees of freedom	1256	

Significantly different from 0 at *** 0.1 %, ** 1 %, * 5 %.

Table 8
Regression on oil heating expenditure ($\ln(\overline{E_H}/HDD)$) without country-specific effects for one percent price increase.

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic
$\ln(I)$	5.6785	74.4***
U_r	-2.4509	-60.2***
F	-1.0369	-32.7***
$Const$	-67.9587	-86.3***
R-squared	0.98	
F-Statistic	2012	
Degrees of freedom	1256	

Significantly different from 0 at *** 0.1 %, ** 1 %, * 5 %.

Table 9
NUTS-3 variables.

Variable	Source	Name
HDD	Eurostat	Heating degree days by NUTS-3 region - Averaged years 2019–2023
Ur	Eurostat	Urban-rural typology (1 = predominantly urban, 0 = predominantly rural, 0.5 = intermediate)
F	Eurostat	Family composition Computed from CENSUS 2011 round on families by type, size and NUTS-3 region
I	Eurostat	Disposable income Computed from disposable income at NUTS-2 level (I_j) and GDP per capita at NUTS-2 (GDP_j) and NUTS-3 level (GDP_i) for year 2015 $I_i = I_j \cdot \frac{GDP_j}{GDP_i}$ with $i \in j$

econometric modeling results with a GIS-based spatial framework at the NUTS-3 level, utilizing data from the Eurostat database. The integration enables the mapping of ETS-2 impacts across 1160 European regions, highlighting areas most affected by increased energy costs.

Exogenous variables used in the regressions are extracted from Eurostat at the NUTS-3 level, requiring extensive efforts to consolidate various data sources, address missing values for certain regions, and harmonize regional definitions in light of changes to names and boundaries. Spatial disaggregation to the NUTS-3 level is performed using methods outlined in Table 9. For regions in countries not represented in the household budget survey, econometric estimates of the impact of a 1 % energy price increase are applied, with adjustments based on the price increases detailed in Table 1.

The average regional increase in energy expenditures due to heating is € 125, while transport-related expenditures average € 185. Both categories exhibit maximum increases of approximately € 500. The distributions of these increases across regions are visualized in Figs. 4 and 5, which provide histograms illustrating the variability in heating and transport costs among regions.

Further regional mapping reveals a somewhat scattered distribution of the impacts across regions. Central European regions, particularly in Germany and Austria, experience higher increases in transport expenditures, as shown in Fig. 6. In contrast, regions in Eastern Europe, such as Poland and Slovenia, exhibit more substantial increases in heating expenditures, as depicted in Fig. 7, underscoring the geographical disparities in energy cost impacts driven by the ETS-2 price.

Regions in Central EU, such as Germany and Austria, are projected to experience higher increases in transport costs under the implementation of the EU ETS-2, driven primarily by their extensive road networks and significant reliance on road transport for goods and passenger mobility (Rodrigue, 2020). Additionally, Germany’s existing national carbon pricing system for heating and road transport may contribute to transitional price adjustments under ETS-2, potentially intensifying short-term cost impacts (Glaser, 2014). It should be noted that while strong industrial sectors in these countries may increase overall vulnerability to transport cost changes, the current analysis does not explicitly model sector-specific price effects. Instead, differences in income levels remain the primary driver of variations in absolute expenditure increases, with wealthier countries generally incurring higher fossil fuel expenditures.

On the other hand, regions in Poland and Slovenia are likely to experience higher increases in heating costs due to their heavy reliance on fossil fuels for heating, particularly coal in Poland, making them more

Fig. 4. Histogram of heating expenditure increase in € by region.

Fig. 5. Histogram of transport expenditure increase in € by region.

Fig. 6. Increase of transport expenditure in € by regions.

Fig. 7. Increase of heating expenditure in € by regions.

vulnerable to carbon pricing (Verma et al., 2023). Additionally, their underdeveloped low-carbon infrastructure, including limited adoption of near-zero emissions buildings and renewable energy systems, hampers their ability to transition away from carbon-intensive heating methods (Peszko et al., 2020). Slovenia’s current carbon tax of € 17 per tonne, significantly lower than the anticipated ETS-2 prices, indicates a larger price jump upon implementation. Furthermore, the absence of stringent national climate policies may lead to a steeper adjustment for these regions as ETS-2 takes effect.

An exposure index was calculated for each region by considering disposable income, where total expenditure increases for transport and heating were divided by disposable income and normalized to values between 0 (not exposed) and 1 (fully exposed). The resulting index, mapped in Fig. 8, reveals significant regional disparities, with Poland, Bulgaria, Hungary, and Slovenia showing notably higher levels of exposure, highlighting substantial inequalities across regions.

The higher exposure indexes observed in certain regions can be attributed to several factors. Lower average disposable incomes in these countries, compared to Western European counterparts, amplify the relative impact of increased transport and heating costs. Additionally, the higher emissions intensity of these regions, driven by colder winters and less efficient building stock, results in greater vulnerability to carbon pricing. Furthermore, some recent reports indicate that without social welfare redistribution mechanisms, fossil gas heating prices in some Eastern European countries could rise by up to 37 %, exacerbating the financial burden on households in these areas (WWF, 2022).

Likewise, Fig. 9 shows the correlation between the exposure index and per capita income across various regions. It clearly reveals an indication that the regions most vulnerable to risk are predominantly among the economically disadvantaged areas within the European Union, characterized by a per capita income of less than 20,000 €.

Fig. 8. Exposed regions.

Fig. 9. Relationship between exposed region and income per capita in € - blue point: computed exposure index - red point: estimated exposure index with a polynomial equation of degree 3 using OLS.

As presented in Table 10, the regions with the highest 10 % exposure are concentrated in Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, and Slovenia. Additionally, several NUTS-3 regions in Austria, Germany, Romania, and Spain are significantly represented within the top 20 %. Overall, a total of 348 regions fall within the top 30 % of the highest exposure index. Notably, no regions from France, Greece, Portugal, or the Netherlands are included in this category.

The findings indicate that regional disparities are partially shaped by country-specific characteristics. A primary factor is the uniform price increase across Member States, largely influenced by existing national taxation frameworks, such as energy excise duties and value-added tax. In addition, domestic energy policies contribute to these differences. Notable examples include the continued reliance on coal for residential heating in coal-abundant countries (Gajdzik et al., 2023), preferential access to Russian natural gas in countries like Hungary, and France’s widespread adoption of electric heating, stemming from a policy-driven commitment to nuclear energy overcapacity (Fontaine, 2021).

Table 10
Top exposed regions by country.

	Top 10%	Top 20%	Top 30%	Number of regions
Austria	6	19	26	35
Belgium	0	5	12	44
Bulgaria	22	27	28	28
Croatia	0	0	0	21
Cyprus	0	0	0	1
Czech Republic	0	1	6	14
Denmark	0	0	0	11
Estonia	0	0	0	5
Finland	0	0	0	19
France	0	0	0	96
Germany	0	42	125	400
Greece	0	0	0	52
Hungary	19	20	20	20
Ireland	0	0	0	8
Italy	0	1	1	107
Latvia	0	0	0	5
Lithuania	0	0	0	10
Luxembourg	0	0	0	1
Malta	0	0	0	2
Netherlands	0	0	0	40
Poland	57	73	73	73
Portugal	0	0	0	26
Romania	2	22	25	42
Slovakia	0	0	0	8
Slovenia	10	12	12	12
Spain	0	10	20	59
Sweden	0	0	0	21
EU27	116	232	348	1160

4.5. Limitations and further improvements

This study faces several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the WILLIAM database employed is somewhat outdated (2015) and does not account for the penetration of CO₂-free technologies in heating and transportation, such as heat pumps, hybrid cars, or electric vehicles. Consequently, the estimated impacts of ETS-2 may be overstated. Moreover, our analysis is static and does not incorporate potential price-induced changes in the energy mix, meaning that our findings are most applicable in the short to medium term. Certain Member States are not included in the WILLIAM database, and the statistical methodology employed to address this limitation may be subject to criticism. Nevertheless, we maintain that our proposed solution is preferable to complete exclusion.

Some European countries have already implemented a carbon taxation. For example, Germany has set up a domestic ETS and adopted a law outlining the transition from the national Emissions Trading System to the EU-wide ETS-2. The energy prices used in our calculations effectively incorporate this CO₂ price, meaning that the increase in energy prices after the implementation of the ETS-2 will be lower if we take this initial carbon price into account. However, it is still a little too early to incorporate this dimension, as most European countries have not yet made a clear decision on the matter. But future studies will need to include it.

Additionally, the study does not evaluate any redistribution mechanisms for ETS-2 revenues. While existing research highlights the importance of redistribution in mitigating distributional effects, its design and implementation are highly complex and fall beyond the scope of this work (Douenne, 2020). Finally, broader dimensions of climate policy impacts, including well-being, employment effects, or job losses, are not considered in the present analysis. Future research could integrate these aspects to provide a more comprehensive assessment of ETS-2.

Our analysis further underscores the necessity of examining the effects of the European energy transition at the regional level, rather than solely at the national level. Such an approach depends on the availability of regional statistical data (NUTS-2 or NUTS-3), which remains fragmented despite ongoing improvements in European statistical frameworks—as exemplified by initiatives such as the Annual Regional Database of the European Commission (ARDECO) (Auteri et al., 2024). Additionally, this endeavor requires advancements in economic modeling tailored to regional analysis. Pioneering efforts in this regard include the RHOMOLO model (Christensen, 2022) and the regional adaptation of the GEM-E3 model (Charalampidis et al., 2019), which represent initial steps toward addressing this methodological gap.

5. Conclusion and policy implications

5.1. Conclusion

The analysis of the EU's Emissions Trading System 2 (ETS-2) presented in this study highlights significant distributional implications across households and regions within Europe. The regressive distributional impacts of ETS-2 align with established findings on carbon pricing inequities (Baranzini et al., 2017), but our spatially disaggregated analysis reveals novel dimensions of vulnerability. While previous studies have primarily examined impacts at the national level (Antosiewicz et al., 2022; Rüb, 2024), our integrated statistical and spatial analysis reveals that rural households in fossil fuel-dependent regions face cost burdens 0.3 to 31 times higher than their urban counterparts. This approach provides a clearer depiction of the intra-country disparities driven by regional determinants.

These impacts are further exacerbated in economically disadvantaged regions, such as those in Central and Eastern Europe, where vulnerabilities are amplified by lower GDP per capita and limited access to energy-efficient infrastructure. The amplified burdens in Central and Eastern Europe corroborate Bouzarovski and Tirado Herrero (2017)'s work on energy peripheries, where low incomes and inefficient housing intersect. Our econometric analysis identifies new vulnerability drivers of fossil-fuel-reliant rural regions possess higher potential for facing heating expenditure increases. Regions with a strong dependence on coal, such as Poland, and those characterized by limited low-carbon infrastructure experience the greatest burdens in heating costs. Furthermore, urban–rural disparities significantly influence variations in transport-related expenditures. In particular, the absence of adequate public transportation in rural Bulgaria heightens sensitivity to fuel price fluctuations, reflecting patterns consistent with the transport poverty framework proposed by Mattioli et al. (2020) and indexed by Primc et al. (2025).

5.2. Policy implications

These findings underscore the need for regionally differentiated policy interventions to ensure a fair distribution of climate transition costs under ETS-2. The SCF, as the EU's primary redistributive mechanism, offers a valuable opportunity to address emerging inequalities. However, its current design may require refinement to better reflect spatial and socio-economic disparities.

First, SCF distribution could be improved by weighting allocations according to regional vulnerability indices. Our analysis shows substantial intra-country variation such as rural regions in Poland facing heating expenditure burdens 46–50 % higher (as a share of income) than urban areas. These disparities reflect differences in income levels, fossil fuel dependence, and urban–rural infrastructure, which uniform allocation rules risk overlooking. Regions with high coal reliance, such as Poland and Bulgaria, are particularly exposed to ETS-2 cost increases and should be prioritized accordingly.

Where SCF resources are allocated for investment, support should target comprehensive energy efficiency measures in the residential sector. Current retrofit rates are insufficient to meet climate goals (Rosenow et al., 2017), and recent work suggests they must at least double (Günther et al., 2025). Support should go beyond basic interventions, such as appliance upgrades or loft insulation to include full-home retrofits, especially in low-income, rural households where the energy savings potential is significant but largely untapped.

Third, ETS-2 is likely to raise transport fuel costs, disproportionately affecting rural households that rely on private vehicles due to limited alternatives (Mattioli et al., 2020). SCF-funded mobility subsidies could mitigate these impacts. Existing national programs, such as Sweden's climate bonus for rural municipalities and France's social leasing scheme for electric vehicles, provide useful models that could be scaled and adapted to high-vulnerability regions across the EU. In addition to vehicle subsidies, SCF could support non-car mobility for vulnerable households through public transport vouchers, discounted seasonal passes, or subsidies for rural transit services. Similar initiatives supported by EU cohesion policy provide relevant examples that Member States could adapt or expand.

Lastly, SCF allocations could adopt a tiered support framework to leverage proven mechanisms. Short-term measures should focus on direct subsidies, such as financial aid for energy bills or rural mobility support, to provide immediate relief for vulnerable households. Medium-term interventions should emphasize energy-related investments, including renovation vouchers for low-emission equipment or full household retrofits. In the long term, SCF resources should align with mandated energy efficiency standards, ensuring structural reductions in energy demand and supporting a sustainable transition.

While ETS-2 is a major step toward meeting the Fit for 55 targets, it revives long-standing equity concerns in EU environmental policy. The findings underscore the possibility that the inherited carbon pricing mechanism of ETS-2 may replicate the shortcomings of earlier EU ETS phases (Bayer and Aklın, 2020), where uneven burdens undermined public support. Future research should evaluate SCF implementation against regional vulnerability metrics, assess policy mixes, such as combining carbon dividends with energy efficiency support and further explore cross-country comparisons to refine vulnerability-based allocation models. Anchoring climate policy in distributive justice, as demonstrated through this regionalized analysis, is essential for building public trust and ensuring the political viability of the EU's green transition.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sigit Perdana: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marc Vielle:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Grammarly in order to improve language and readability. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. List of variables in the wiliam european household database

See Table A.11.

Table A.11
List of variables.

Code	Name
Country	Country
q_income	Income quintiles
v_income	Income ventiles
urb_rur	Population density level
type_household	Type of household
hh_weights	Households
n_pers	Population
n_esOECD	Equivalent household size (modified OECD scale, 1994)
n_children	Children
n_adult	Adults
n_retiree	Retirees
m_age	Average age of household members
n_rooms	Number of rooms available to the household
car	Households with car
P3	Final consumption expenditure
CP011	Food
CP012	Non-alcoholic beverages
CP021_22_23	Alcoholic beverages; tobacco; and narcotics
CP031	Clothing
CP032	Footwear
CP041_42	Actual rentals for housing; imputed rentals for housing
CP043_44	Maintenance and repair of the dwelling; water supply and miscellaneous services relating to the dwelling
CP045	Electricity, gas and other fuels
CP0451	Electricity
CP0452	Gas
CP0453	Liquid fuels
CP0454	Solid fuels
CP0455	Heat energy
CP051	Furniture and furnishings, carpets and other floor coverings
CP052	Household textiles
CP053	Household appliances
CP054	Glassware, tableware and household utensils
CP055	Tools and equipment for house and garden
CP056	Goods and services for routine household maintenance
CP061	Medical products, appliances and equipment
CP062_63	Out-patient services; hospital services
CP071	Purchase of vehicles
CP072	Operation of personal transport equipment
CP0721	Spare parts and accessories
CP0722	Fuels and lubricants
CP0723	Maintenance and repair of personal transport equipment
CP0724	Other services in respect of personal transport equipment

(continued on next page)

Table A.11 (continued)

Code	Name
CP073	Transport services
CP0731	Passenger transport by railway
CP0732	Passenger transport by road
CP0733	Passenger transport by air
CP0734	Passenger transport by sea and inland waterway
CP0735	Combined passenger transport
CP0736	Other purchased transport services
CP081_82_83	Postal services; telephone and telefax equipment; telephone and telefax services
CP091	Audio-visual, photographic and information processing equipment
CP092	Other major durables for recreation and culture
CP093	Other recreational items and equipment, gardens and pets
CP094_95_96	Recreational and cultural services; newspapers, books and stationery; package holidays
CP101_102_103_104_105	Education
CP111	Catering services
CP112	Accommodation services
CP121_122_123_124_125_126_127	Personal care; prostitution; personal effects n.e.c.; social protection; insurance; financial services n.e.c.; other services n.e.c.
D11_B3G	Gross wages and salaries and gross mixed income
D12_D61	Social security contributions
B2G	Gross operating surplus
D4_received	Property income received
D4_paid	Property income paid
D51_D59	Taxes
D62	Social benefits other than social transfers in kind
D7_rec	Other current transfers received
D7_paid	Other current transfers paid
D8	Adjustment for the change in pension entitlements
P51C	Consumption of fixed capital
B6G	Disposable income, gross
B6N	Disposable income, net
B8G	Saving, gross
B8N	Saving, net
B8G	Saving, gross
B8N	Saving, net
NF_ASS	Non-financial assets
F_ASS	Financial assets
LIAB	Liabilities
NW	Net wealth

Appendix B. Additional figures

See Figs. B.10–B.16.

Fig. B.10. Increase of heating expenditure in % of disposable income per location of household (rural and urban) and country.

Fig. B.11. Increase of transport expenditure in % of disposable income per location of household (rural and urban) and country.

Fig. B.12. Increase of heating expenditure in % of disposable income per family composition and country.

Fig. B.13. Increase of transport expenditure in % of disposable income per family composition and country.

Fig. B.14. Histogram of heating expenditure increase in € by region weighted by population.

Data availability

Data will be made available upon request.

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Fig. B.15. Histogram of transport expenditure increase in € by region weighted by population.

Fig. B.16. Increase of energy expenditure in € by regions.

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